

DRUM

Drivers of Resistance in Uganda & Malawi

Standard Operating Procedure	Version: 2
Household Environmental Sample Collection	
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Version History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	01/04/19	Initial version
2.0	01/07/19	Changes made after pilot phase

1. Introduction

The method described is applicable to the collection of environmental samples including food, water, clothing, soil and food preparation surfaces from households in the DRUM study.

The proportion of patients admitted to hospitals in Uganda and Malawi with invasive infections caused by ESBL resistant Enterobacteriaceae including ESBL E coli (ESBL-E) and ESBL K pneumoniae (ESBL-K) is increasing. Given the reduced availability of Carbapenems, many of these drug-resistant infections are locally untreatable. To understand the drivers of this antimicrobial resistance, further evidence of the role of household environment contamination on human and animal carriage with ESBL-E and ESBL-K is required.

2. Purpose

These methods describe the process of collecting environmental samples from households included in the DRUM study, which will be subsequently screened for the presence of ESBL *E. coli* / *K. pneumoniae*.

3. Responsibilities

- Field workers
 - Collection of environmental samples according to this SOP
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Prompt transport of collected samples to the laboratory
 - Completion of sample collection log
- Core Laboratory Technicians
 - Receive samples from field and complete sample collection log
 - Register samples on DRUM teleform LIMS system
 - Inform Study Laboratory Technicians of sample arrival
- Study Laboratory Technicians
 - Ensure prompt collection of study samples from laboratory reception
 - Double-check correct sample labelling as in this SOP

- Principal Investigators
 - Ensure field worker training in sample collection processes is provided
 - Undertake quality control checks of sample collection and processing.

4. Procedure - Water Sample Collection

4.1. Materials and Equipment needed

Gloves

Autoclavable Nalgene bottles

Sterile collection bags

Hand disinfectant

4.2. Water Sample Collection Method

- Up to 3x samples of water should be collected from a household (and labelled appropriately). These will likely include 1) Drinking water, 2) Water for cooking, and 3) Water for cleaning or 4) Household rinse water (**Figure 1**).
- Furthermore, 1x river water sample should also be taken (**Figure 2**), if not already included.

1. It is likely that households acquire water from different sources due to the cost and weight of kiosk water, and this diversity should be captured.
 - *Source Drinking water*: This should be the most commonly used drinking water, whether from a household tap, kiosk, pump or river.
 - *The water should be collected from source, not from a storage vessel inside the house. For example, if they get water from a kiosk, go to the kiosk that they use for sampling.*
 - *Household stored drinking water*: This will be water from these areas that has been stored in some sort of storage vessel, depending on the household. This could be from a jerry can, bowl, or bottle.
 - *“Other water”*: This refers to a sample of water that is used by the household, that is ideally acquired from a different source to that of the drinking water.

- Water received from taps or collection storage vessels within the household should be directly poured into the bottle rather than dipped.
 - Where possible a total volume of 500mL should be obtained, and reasons for collection of <500mL should be stated on the electronic record.
- Once the water sample has been obtained the bottle should be securely closed and stored in a container protected from sunlight for transport to the laboratory (see section 10).

4.2.2: Grab/rinse sample collection method

- A grab/rinse water sample will involve asking all household members to place their hands into a sterile bowl filled with 500ml of water in.
 - Ask them to each rinse their hands, using the water in the bowl
 - Once all members have rinsed their hands in the water, collect the rinse-water in a pre-autoclaved 500ml or 1L Nalgene bottle.

4.2.3: River water sample identification.

- 1x river water sample should be collected as part of the household sampling.
- Where river water is used by the household and stored in the house for use, river water should be sampled both in the household and also from the direct river site that the house interacts with.
 - For this sample the household should be asked if they ever come into contact with river water, whether it be for use in drinking, cleaning, bathing or children playing. If they answer in the affirmative, then a sample of river water should be sourced from the location where they obtain the water / interact with the river most commonly (Figure 2).
 - Directions to this source should be obtained from the household or physically shown if possible.
 - The process of river water sampling is described in a separate SOP (River water sampling).

Figure 2. River water sampling.

5. Procedure - Environmental Swabbing

5.1. Materials and Equipment needed

Gloves

3M sponge-sticks stored in BPW

3M swabs stored in BPW

Hand disinfectant

5.2. Environmental Swabbing Method

- Choose 3x sites for sampling.
 - These sites should be guided by the observational field worker in the intensive households, and through the judgement of the field staff in follow-up and sparse households.
 - Priorities will be around areas associated with hand contact zones, and food handling.
 - The priority list for swabbing of areas (dependant on the observations) are:

- I. Door handles
- II. Fridge handles
- III. Chopping Board / food preparation surface
- IV. Rags / wasters used for washing cloth
- V. Knife / cutlery handles
- Other risk specific contact zones should be included dependant on the observer.
- For each area identified choose either a separate 3M sponge stick or swab.

5.2.1: 3M Sponge-Stick.

1. Wear gloves and appropriate PPE.
2. Ensure that an aseptic technique is used throughout the procedure and do not touch the sponge with anything other than the surface that is being tested.
3. Firstly, open the sterile bag and move the handle of the swab to the top using the **outside** of the bag.
4. Then continuing to use the outside of the bag, squeeze the sponge to remove roughly 10ml of buffered peptone water into the bottom of the bag. Set the bag aside (with the BPW in)
5. Manoeuvre the handle to the outside of the bag, and then grab the handle with your hand, ensuring not to touch the sponge.
6. Wipe the first side of the sponge over a 30cm x 30cm area surface that has been selected in a horizontal fashion.
7. Turn the sponge over and wipe the same area with the reverse side of the sponge, but this time vertically.
8. Place the sponge back into the sterile bag, containing the buffered peptone water, and while handling the outside of the bag remove the sponge from the handle by gently pulling from side to side. (Do not place the handle or your hand inside the bag during this process).
9. Discard to handle and seal the bag. Ensure that the sponge is now soaked in the buffered peptone water.
10. Clearly label the site from where the swab was taken.
11. Place the bag (with the sponge inside) into a container for transport to the laboratory (see section 10)

5.2.2: 3M Swab.

1. Ensure that an aseptic technique is used throughout the procedure and do not touch the swab with anything other than the surface that is being tested.
2. Firstly, open the swab tube, and remove the swab from the BPW (making sure not to spill the BPW).
3. Wipe the swab over a 5cm x 5cm area surface that has been selected in a horizontal fashion.
4. Turn the swab over and wipe the same area with the reverse side of the sponge, but this time vertically.
5. Place the swab back into the tube, containing the BPW, ensuring that the swab is now soaked in the BPW.
6. Clearly label the site from where the swab was taken.
7. Place the tube into a bag, and then place the bag into a container for transport to the laboratory (see section 10)

6. Procedure - Food Sample Collection

6.1. Materials and Equipment needed

Gloves

Sterile collection bags

Sterile collection bags (with BPW)

Hand disinfectant

6.2. Food Sample Collection Method

A total of 2x separate food samples are to be taken per household. Where there is no food available within a household attempt to take extra environmental swabs

- Using gloves and aseptic technique, place a sample of food into a sterile Whirl-pac collection bag (without BPW). For multiple food samples please place food into individual bags and ensure care not to cross contaminate.
- The priority when choosing food samples should be in the following order:
 - Fresh vegetables (uncooked) and fresh fruit.

- Do not collect other items such fresh meat, dried meat or fish, stored nsima or milk products.
 - The reason for this prioritization is to consider contamination from water and the surrounding local environment
 - Also, milk-based products require different processing techniques.
- For fruit, take the whole item and place it into the bag. Do not use peeled fruit or cut pieces of fruit (as the presence of citrus can inhibit the microbiological growth).
- For vegetables, any size item that fits into the bag will suffice.
- Label each bag with the name of the food item, location of acquisition (Shop / Local Market / Own plot), time and person collecting the sample. If possible, take a photo of the food item obtained.
- Place the sample in a container, protected from sunlight for transport to the laboratory (*see section 10*)

7. Procedure - Clothing Sample Collection

7.1. Materials and Equipment needed

Gloves

3M sponge-stick in BPW

Hand disinfectant

7.2. Clothing Sample Collection

1x sample of clothing should be obtained

- Consent from the household member providing the clothing should be obtained prior to acquisition.
- The household member should then be informed that the swab will not harm the material and that once the dress has been swabbed that it should be considered dirty and that it should be washed before being re-worn.
- The primary item of clothing of interest is the chitenji worn by the woman who looks after the children (and/or) prepares and cooks the food.

- A 3M sponge-stick (in buffered peptone water) should then be taken of an old, unwashed / yesterday's chitenji, focussing on the area that is used for wiping the mouths of children or used for cleaning surfaces or food items.
- The process of how to swab is described in 5.2
- After acquiring the swab please store the sample in a container, protected by light, as described in section 10, and return the chitenji back to the household member, reiterating that it should be washed before being re-worn.

8. Procedure - Soil Sample Collection

8.1. Materials and Equipment needed

Gloves

Boot socks

Sterile Whirl-pac collection bags

Hand disinfectant

8.2. Soil Sample Collection

[1x Boot-sock sample should be taken of household floor \(inside/outside\)](#)

1. Using gloves, place 1x boot sock over your right foot
2. Again, using gloves, place a second boot sock over the initial one on your right foot, ensuring that the second sock does not go over the edges of the first one.
3. Walk around the household floor, particularly the kitchen, eating environments and around any areas of animal exposure for roughly 1 minute. This may include areas outside of the household walls.
4. Then, take the outer sock off (using gloves), and place into a whirl pac bag, and seal it.
5. Discard the second boot sock.
6. Place the Whirl pac bag into a sealed container for transport to the laboratory (see section 10).

9. Procedure - Drain Sample Collection

9.1 Materials and Equipment needed

Gloves

30ml universal container

Sterile collection bags

9.2 Drain Sample Collection

- 1) Wear personal protective equipment throughout, including gloves and boots.
- 2) Identify a suitable drain sample from outside the household (either close to the house, or within the household compound).
 - a. A drain is defined as water in motion either in a constructed drain (dug or built) or moving on a surface.
- 3) While wearing gloves, submerge the 30ml universal container into the drain fluid until at least 2-3ml has been obtained.
- 4) Seal the container tightly, and decontaminate the outside.
- 5) The drain sample should then be clearly labelled and placed into a sealable plastic bag and placed into a container for transport to the laboratory (see section 10).

10. Sample Receipt and Storage

Protect all samples from direct sunlight and transport in an insulated container or refrigerator at 2 – 8°C. Samples should be analysed as soon as is practicable and storage under the above conditions should not exceed 24 h before the commencement of analysis.

11. Health and Safety

Please refer to risk assessment tools and local health and safety guidelines

Environmental Sampling in Household

Water Sampling in Household

